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DEVELOPMENT OF STRATEGIC DESIGN MANAGEMENT TOOLS IN COLOMBIAN AND SPANISH SME'S

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ABSTRACT

For years, the role of design has been understood as something purely aesthetic, and its true potential has not been realized. However some companies have managed to incorporate the design as a strategic factor in their processes to provide higher value products to consumers.

Design management facilitates the integration of business and design strategies, as well as helps to obtain products aligned with market requirements, by organizing and documenting methodologically the Design Process, often regarded as informal due to its high level of creativity.

Several studies carried out in the footwear and leather goods sector in Bogotá, Colombia, and in the wooden furniture sector in Asturias, Spain, have revealed the urgent need of the Design Process in the SMEs to distinguish their products from the competitors. In this sense, the main problems of those companies are the identification of the value of Design, weaknesses in Design management and the lack of knowledge for applying the Design in their strategy in order to obtain competitive advantage.

Keywords: Strategic Design Management, SMEs, support tools.

INTRODUCTION

International experience shows that “the cost of materials and manufacturing processes correspond to 95% of the production cost of a manufactured product, however it is only incorporated in 30% of the final price, while the design cost of the product corresponds to 5% of production, but affects 70% of the remaining final price” (Brown et al, 1999).

The incorporation of design for the development of new products is considered for the SME's in the subsectors of footwear and leather goods in Bogotá D.C. and wooden furniture in Asturias, featuring the use of low technology, abundant workforce, potential exporters and high turnover of products, of lesser importance, as they have concentrated their efforts in competing for a low price in spite of not having an adequate productive capacity, and facing continues high cost of raw materials and the strong competition of those countries that have a cheaper workforce (Paredes and López, 2008).

Due to those common problems, a collaborative project between the two countries was launched in order to develop information Design tools to facilitate SMEs to integrate it as a strategic advantage, once this problem was detected with strong similarities in both sectors.

This article shows partial results of the project, carried out in cooperation between Spain and Colombia, in which Design support tools have been jointly developed for strategic management of the Design process that allows incorporating the design and the development process into the new products in SME's.

The work done until now is been implemented in interactive digital tools that are been developed at the moment in Colombia, and that will be finished at the end of this year and accessible through a website to the companies in Spanish.

DEVELOPMENT OF TOOLS

The fundamental objective of the project consisted in spreading and making Asturian and Colombian companies aware of the importance of the design management. This was done through the creation of interactive digital tools which facilitates the SME's in those countries in the design process, development and the preparation of sales of new products, both in the strategic and operative level in order to increase their competitiveness.

Nowadays, the few tools that exist are centered in the auto diagnostic of design which is a fundamental stage to visualize the level of integration of design in the company. After a long research, the shortage of tools involved within this area of knowledge became evident, as well as for the design and development of new products.

The project was divided in two stages: an auto-diagnosis tool to determine the status of SMEs in designing, and a second one concerned with the hold process of design and product development from defining the type of product to be launched on the market through the strategic definition up to the pre-marketing. The structure of the project it is outlined in figure 1.

TOOL 1: AUTO DIAGNOSTIC

By means of an audit (corporate, of design and of product), the initial state of the SME's was determined in relation to the design management.

Figure 2. Auto diagnostic tool main page.

For an optimum design and a more comprehensive development of auto diagnostic tool, a revision of the various existing tools of auto diagnostic design was made.

Figure 1. Interactive digital tools structure.

In the interactive tool of auto diagnostic five analytic categories have been defined:

- Corporate culture
- Strategic focus of design
- Visualization of the market
- Organization of design
- Design and development of products and/or services

These categories are divided into types and establish the relationships between maximums and minimums, generating combinations in relation to the answers from the users and giving as result a diagnosis and its pertinent recommendations (Figure 3).

Once this interactive auto diagnostic tool was developed, an evaluation of the functioning of the tool was made with the SME's by means of the application and validity of the usability test, contrasting the information obtained between Spain and Colombia and solving the errors detected, which served to improve the tool and its usability.

DESIGN AND PRODUCT DEVELOPMENT TOOLS AT SME'S

To define the different tools involved in the design and development of the product the following references were taken (Figure 4):

Figure 4. Phases in Process Design. Fundación PRODINTEC.

From these fundamental bases, in the framework of the present project, four digital interactive instruments have been developed which facilitates the organization of the design process of new products in the SME's, in such a way that the uncertainty is minimized and facilitates to take decisions in SME's during the above process.

Each of these four instruments are composed of different sections by means of which the designer/company can take note using information cards, on the situation which has been presented, thus bringing in relative data of the phase in which it is situated at that moment.

These four interactive digital tools can be used either in an independent form or as a combined one by the participating companies. These tools will be outlined in the following paragraphs.

Figure 3. Auto diagnostic results and recommendations.

Tool2: Strategic Definition

Tool number two has as purpose to facilitate the identification of those products which are to be marketed, analyzing aspects that have to do with the environment, competition, needs and desires of the consumer and the differentiating elements of the new products, among others.

Figure 5. Navigation map of the Strategic definition tool.

This tool includes five sections:

- Chronogram
- The environment situation (macro, micro and consumer)

Figure 6. Strategic definition tool. Environment situation section.

- Strategic definition (attributes of the product and strategic circle)
- Strategic concept
- Planning of the line of products

Tool 3: Conceptual Design

This third tool gives useful information to define the concept of the new product and has as its objective the guiding of the creative phase looking at the choice of alternatives of design for the new line or collection of products for the company.

This tool includes five sections:

- Initial information
- Trends (trends and attributes)

Figure 7. Conceptual design tool. Trends section.

Figure 8. Conceptual design tool. Example in Trends section.

- Emotional (adjectives and panel of sensations)
- Sketches (alternatives of design and panel of consumers)
- Concept of product line

Tool4: Pre-production

This tool has as purpose to guide the development of the alternatives in the previous conceptual tool. Technical specifications will be decided on which the models can be constructed including plans, material specifications, construction of prototypes and testing, in such a way that the technical solutions can be converted into manufacturing solutions.

Figure 9. Pre-production tool. Initial information section.

This tool includes five sections:

- Initial information
- Detail design (specifications and restrictions)

Figure 10. Pre-production tool. Testing and verification section.

- Product engineering (model and analysis of the economic strategy)
- Testing and verification (product tests)
- Final documentation (prototype and final documentation)

Tool5: Pre-marketing

Tool number five has the purpose of guiding the phase previous to commercializing, showing the steps to take to market the product. It defines the communication of the selling of the new product, and the means of assistance.

This tool includes three sections:

- Initial information
- Strategy

Figure 11. Pre-marketing tool. Initial information section.

- Evaluation

The contents of these tools were also tested with the participating companies with the objective of assuring the usability.

CONCLUSIONS

The development of the tools of the project: auto diagnostic and design and product development tools (including strategic definition, conceptual design, pre-production and pre-marketing phases), has been a process which has allowed a continuous feedback with participating companies in the project, and from this the following conclusions has been reached:

- *The use of the tools improves the self-knowledge of the company.*

Regarding the company it should be noted that the use of the tools has instigated an important process of reflection in the design and product development team which helps for a better knowledge of the same company and its environment and allows it to face up the changes and problems that may appear.

- *Auto diagnostic tool helps the companies to visualize mistakes and to correct them.*

The carrying out of the auto diagnosis of design, as well as the recommendations given in this project, aid the managers to visualize the mistakes which are habitually made or the problems which have to be faced in the moment of the execution of different tasks of design in the company, and help to apply means of correction that have previously been ignored.

- *Companies need a systematic process to implement the design especially in strategic definition.*

Further on from the manufacturing of a product the companies require a systematic process to guide and implement the design, from its same strategic definition, because it is exactly there where values are established which will help in the differentiating. If the necessary importance is not given at this stage, the arguments backing up the product will be based on advantages easily imitated by the competition.

- *The use of the tools will help the companies to better know the consumers.*

The use of these tools, where there is a lot of small and necessary field work involved to have a better insight of the market, will help the companies to create a constant dynamic knowledge of the consumers and will allow them to design products which will be closer to their ever-changing style of life.

- *Tools improve both internal and external management of the design process.*

The constant processes of feedback with the companies has shown that independent of his size, a SME's can improve both his internal and external processes of managing the design in a more suitable way.

- *Team work helps to develop strategies at a global level.*

Working in a team helps healthy discussion with the confronting of ideas and the construction of strategies and new postures from the information and from agreement, a situation which improves the perception that the company has of design, going from a level which is intrinsically individual in the work of the designer, to a level of negotiation and responsibility which involves the hold organization.

- *It's essential to reinforce initial stages to create competitive advantages.*

It is necessary to keep on reinforcing the initial stages of the process of design and product development, because it is in those stages where values of differentiation are established which aid to create competitive advantages.

The tools developed and tested in this project have been specifically focused on the SME's of footwear and leather goods in Bogotá, Colombia and wooden furniture in Asturias, Spain.

In order to apply these tools to other sectors it would be necessary to carry out a previous study of them to establish significant differences from those SME's already studied, taking into account the points in common and making the necessary adjustments both in the conceptual level as in the programming, which would require a new process of evaluation.

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